

MATRIX CRACKING BEHAVIOUR OF OFF-AXIS PLIES IN GLASS-EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This is the first part of a wider study on the effect of ply orientation on matrix cracking behaviour. The response of $[0/90]_n$ and $[0/60]_n$ glass-epoxy laminates under tensile loading are presented in terms of stiffness loss and crack propagation. A method for accurately measuring crack growth and locating each crack is introduced.

INTRODUCTION

Most work on matrix cracking has focused on the relatively simple $[0/90]$ family of laminates [eg 1,2,3]. Using shear-lag or similar models, the reduction in the laminate modulus associated with cracking can be predicted. These models can also explain ply thickness dependence on crack density. They are, however, limited to cross-ply laminates with one cracked layer. Although more sophisticated models are now available [eg 4,5] to deal with more complicated systems, it is generally recognized that a good approach to solving the crack problem is by using fracture mechanics concepts. The use of fracture mechanics in delamination studies is now commonplace. The criterion for delamination crack propagation can be expressed in terms of either G , the strain energy release rate or K , the stress intensity factor. Some workers [eg 6] have attempted to use K but G is preferred [eg 7,8] to avoid dealing with the mathematical complexity of the singularity at the crack tip.

In this work, it is believed that the same approach can be applied to matrix cracking since delamination is matrix-dominated. Others have also taken this attitude [eg 2]. Transverse ply-cracking in the $[0/90]_n$ lay-up is fairly well understood, but the cracking behaviour of an off-axis layer is still unclear. Such knowledge is necessary as realistic lay-ups have many ply orientations. Currently, the lack of a comprehensive set of data presents an obstacle in developing new models or verifying existing ones. Therefore, the intent here is to first obtain systematically a set of experimental results and then try to characterise the matrix cracking behaviour of an off-axis layer using fracture mechanics concepts.

This work describes a limited set of experiments using a simple $[0/\theta]_n$ configuration where θ is the off-axis angle. As the laminate is not symmetric (though it is balanced), a shear coupling exists in the laminate when subjected to tension. This coupling is most pronounced when $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$ but disappears as θ tends to 90° . In tension, the shear coupling causes the flat specimen to tend to rotate but it is restricted by the stationary grips. Hence, a slightly non-uniform state of stress is applied. However, this can be minimized if a large specimen aspect ratio (length-to-width ratio greater than 6) is used [9].

The formation of matrix cracks throughout the off-axis ply creates a pattern. This pattern is easily visible in translucent glass-epoxy laminates and can be photographed. A method has been developed to accurately measure the crack growth and identify the cracking sequence. In addition, stiffness losses associated with this matrix cracking in $[0/90]_n$ and $[0/60]_n$ laminates have been measured. With both normal and shear stresses present in the off-axis plies, matrix

cracking involves combined opening (Mode I) and shearing (Mode II) modes. By varying the off-axis angle, the ratio of G_I and G_{II} can be varied and the resultant cracking behaviour observed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

FABRICATION

Specimens were fabricated from E-glass roving which was wet filament wound using EPON 828 epoxy resin with 40 percent Ancamine K1784 Hardener. $[0]_4$, $[90]_4$, $[0/90]_2$, and $[0/60]_2$ laminates were made up from wet unidirectional prepreg and autoclave cured at 122 °F for 3 hours. After post-curing for 3 days, the 28 cm by 18 cm panels were cut oversize into tensile specimens 2.54 cm wide and 25.4 cm long, using a diamond saw. The edges of these specimens were then polished to size on 600 grit silicon carbide paper and finished with optical grade cerium oxide. The four-ply laminates have an average thickness of 0.7 mm and nominal fiber volume of 60%. As the chosen resin system has a refractive index closely matched with the glass fibres, the specimens are translucent.

TENSILE TESTS

Incremental tensile tests were conducted at room temperature using an Instron testing machine at a constant cross-head displacement rate of 0.02 mm/s. The specimen length between the grips was 203mm. A linear voltage displacement transducer (LVDT) was mounted onto the specimen to measure displacements over a 60.52 mm gauge length. In each test, the load was increased incrementally, and after each increment the load-displacement response was monitored and the stiffness calculated. Simultaneously, a photographic record of the off-axis ply crack pattern was taken. To achieve this, a high intensity focussed light was placed on one side of the cracked laminate and a 4x5 Polaroid camera on the other. This procedure was repeated until the specimen failed.

CRACK GROWTH MEASUREMENT

After much experimentation, the following method was developed : the polaroid negatives are magnified four times into positives using a high contrast filter; each photograph is divided into ten frames; using a TASIC Image Analyzer, each crack is detected and its crack length measured on each frame by the analyzer computer; the total crack length is the sum of the length of all the cracks in the ten frames; the image analyzer is also programmed to identify each crack by a set of x-y coordinates. In this manner, the order in which the cracks appear, and their location within the gauge length is recorded accurately.

After all the results from each photograph are collected, a computer program is used to rejoin all ten frames and recalculate the new coordinates of any crack that straddles a frame boundary. These values are then used to plot the crack patterns for each incremental load. This method is similar, but perhaps more detailed than that described in reference [3].

RESULTS

The unidirectional glass-epoxy laminates have the following material properties:

$$E_{11} = 35.0 \text{ GPa}, E_{22} = 10.8 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.29$$

Normalised stiffness reduction for the $[0/90]_2$ lay-up and the corresponding total crack length are plotted as a function of increasing applied tensile stress in Figure 1. The normalised stiffness is cross-plotted against total crack length in Figure 2. Similarly, the results for the $[0/60]_2$ laminate are shown in Figures 3 and 4. The crack patterns drawn from the digitized x-y coordinates of all the individual cracks are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 1. Stiffness reduction and crack length as a function of applied stress in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate.

Figure 2. Stiffness reduction as a function of crack length in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate.

Figure 3. Stiffness change and crack length as a function of applied stress in the $[0/60]_s$ laminate.

Figure 4. Stiffness change as a function of crack length in the $[0/60]_s$ laminate.

Figure 5. Crack pattern in the 90° ply of the [0/90]_s laminate after loading to (a)180 MPa (b)202 MPa (c)229 MPa (d)443 MPa.

Figure 6. Crack pattern in the 60° ply of the [0/60]_s laminate after loading to (a)223 MPa (b)283 MPa (c)307 MPa (d)335 MPa.

DISCUSSION

In Figure 1, the onset of observable matrix cracking in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate occurs at about 180 MPa with a corresponding reduction in stiffness. With increasing load, the transverse cracks accumulate, causing further reductions in the stiffness of the laminate. The same trend is seen for the $[0/60]_s$ laminate (Figure 3) but the rate of decrease in stiffness is slightly slower. Matrix cracking begins at about 223 MPa. In contrast to the cross-ply laminate, the stiffness increases initially by 7 percent (perhaps due to the rotation of the 60° fibres towards the load axis) before a reduction is seen. An initial increase would agree with Laminated Plate Theory predictions but the observed value is rather high.

In Figure 2, the stiffness in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate decreases linearly with the measured crack length. These results are in good agreement with other work [eg 2]. The relationship for the $[0/60]_s$ lay-up (Figure 4), however, is not as simple. If the initial stiffness increase is taken into account, the total stiffness reduction is about 18 percent, similar to that observed for the $[0/90]_s$ lay-up. However, the rate of reduction is not constant.

The crack patterns shown in Figures 5 and 6 show that cracking is not uniform throughout the specimen gauge length. Some areas are more prone to cracking while others do not begin to crack until very high loads are reached. There is a wide range of crack lengths in both specimens and the crack spacing varies along the gauge length. In order to explain these observations, a thorough statistical analysis in terms of crack spacing, average crack length and crack tip interactions will have to be performed.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Stiffness reduction is linearly related to matrix crack growth in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate. The relationship is not as simple for the $[0/60]_s$ lay-up.
2. A method for measuring and recording crack length using image analysis has been developed. With this method, the sequence of occurrence and the location of each individual crack can be identified. The results can then be used for statistical analysis.

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